

Extracellular microbial proteases with specificity for plant proteins in food fermentation

Lise Friis Christensen^{a,*}, Beatriz García-Béjar^b, Claus Heiner Bang-Berthelsen^a, Egon Bech Hansen^a

^a National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Kemitorvet, DK-2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

^b Department of Analytical Chemistry and Food Technology, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Camilo José Cela Avenue, 13071 Ciudad Real, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Plant-based food products are generating a growing interest as part of the ongoing transition to a primarily plant-based diet, which makes demands to the quality, functionality, and health properties of plant proteins. Microbes used for traditional food fermentations such as lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and fungi (yeasts and molds) carry out enzymatic changes on their protein substrates by which technological and sensorial characteristics can be improved. The literature on extracellular proteases targeting plant proteins, on the other hand, is scattered with only a narrow representation of plants even for traditionally plant-based products. Therefore, this review aims to explore the current state of knowledge regarding the application potential of microbial extracellular proteases targeting plant proteins, with a focus on traditional applied food microbes. Plant proteins are targeted by proteolytic microbes of both animal and plant origins, and their proteases show a wide range of activities. Extracellular microbial proteases can hydrolyze specific protein-based allergens and even reduce the toxicity of plant proteins. Additionally, microbial assisted proteolysis can improve plant protein digestibility by increasing availability of peptides and amino acids. This catabolic process will change the organoleptic characteristics of fermented plant proteins, and the release of bioactive peptides can provide additional functionalities to the plant matrix. The proteolytic activity is determined by the microbial strain, and it can be quite substrate selective, which is why proteases may be overlooked by the prevalent use of casein as substrate in proteolytic screenings. The synergistic effects of LAB and fungal species consortia can facilitate and steer plant protein hydrolysis by which co-fermentation may increase or change the properties of plant protein hydrolysates. Microbes do not necessarily require extracellular proteases because endogenous proteases in a plant-matrix may meet the microbial amino acid requirements. However, extracellular proteases have the potential to provide central properties to diverse food-matrices by which the full proteolytic potential of food microbes needs to be explored in order to facilitate the development of high-quality plant-based food products.

1. Introduction

Fermentation is an ancient method of preserving perishable food products. A wide range of species, including bacteria, yeast, and molds, have a long history of beneficial use in food fermentations, including the fermentation of plant raw materials (Bourdichon et al., 2012). This process has been accepted by humans owing to the positive sensorial and technological changes of foods, which have allowed for the development of a wide variety of food products thanks to the various fermentative pathways of microorganisms (Steinkraus, 2004). The periodic table of

fermented foods by Gänzle, 2022 shows this global diversity of fermented food products where a considerable part of the fermented foods are plant-based with the use of diverse microorganisms. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) appear to dominate the bacteria group in food fermentation, and LAB, yeast and filamentous fungi species appear to be the central microbiological workhorses of both plant- and animal-based food fermentation. The taxonomy of the LAB genus *Lactobacillus* has been continuously reorganized with the most recent update in 2020 (Zheng et al., 2020). This review makes use of the current taxonomy.

The fermentation of plants has traditionally been applied as a

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: lisf@food.dtu.dk (L.F. Christensen), beatriz.gbermejo@uclm.es (B. García-Béjar), claban@food.dtu.dk (C.H. Bang-Berthelsen), egbh@food.dtu.dk (E.B. Hansen).

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method of preservation but has also gained appreciation as a way to improve the nutritional value and organoleptic quality. The plant-based food products experience a growing interest. To meet the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, a dietary transition from primarily animal-based towards plant-based protein products is required (Aiking and de Boer, 2020). It is proposed that the current Western dietary patterns can be improved by reducing protein and calorie overconsumption, reducing food waste, and replacing animal-based products with plant-based products. The tendency of protein overconsumption is observed particularly in the Western diet, where a 10–15 % reduction in the protein intake per capita by 2050 has been stated as an aim (Fig. 1). At the same time, the plant-based protein content should increase from 40 % to 60 % of the total food proteins in the diet (Aiking and de Boer, 2020). These objectives impose requirements to the quality, functionality, nutritional value and toxicity of the plant proteins, thereby necessitating new food development strategies (Day, 2013). Hydrolysis of plant proteins is one approach for expanding the utilization catalog of plant proteins because proteolysis may release peptides with valuable bioactivities or cleave allergenic compounds (Day, 2013). The properties of the plant protein hydrolysate strongly depend on the selected protease and the choice of reaction condition. The emulsification, foaming and gel formation properties of the proteins can also be released through specific hydrolysis, whereas such functionalities may be lost

through unspecific or heavy hydrolysis. Olsen et al., 2020 has described an algorithm to identify antioxidant peptides embedded within the sequences of native proteins. Bioinformatics and specific hydrolysis have been used to identify and release emulsifying and antioxidant peptides from potato, seaweed, and single cell proteins (García-Moreno et al., 2020a; Yesiltas et al., 2021).

Microbes traditionally used in fermented food have shown valuable proteolytic activities as part of their fermentation processes. The fermentation involves multiple reactions to convert complex substrates into simple compounds, including microbiological, enzymatic, chemical, biochemical, and physical processes. These complex biosystems contain enzymes from both raw materials and microorganisms that are in charge of hydrolysis reactions such as proteolysis (Bourdichon et al., 2012; Joshi et al., 2018). Some microbes produce extracellular proteases, which are either bound to the microbial cell envelope or secreted. These proteases degrade environmental proteins to facilitate microbial growth, but the process may also support food developments as particularly described for dairy and meat products. However, the information on extracellular proteases of microbes targeting plant-based proteins is rare and scattered even for the traditional plant-based products as sourdough, wine, and sauerkraut. This is also illustrated in Fig. 2 in which the innovation curves for plant- and animal-based dairy products are represented as publications in PubMed (February 2022). This

Fig. 1. Green protein transition including plant protein and hydrolysis

A) The diagram illustrates how the Western world's ongoing green protein transition should progress in order to reach the UN's sustainable development goals. This includes a 10–15 % reduction in the total protein intake per capita over the time frame depicted. The figure numbers appear in Aiking and de Boer, 2020. B) Extracellular proteases (scissors) of three groups of food microbes, including lactic acid bacteria (LAB), yeast, and mold, have traditionally hydrolyzed animal proteins (orange chain of pearls). The bioprocessed protein hydrolysis can both induce (↑) or remove (↓) protein properties. Similar properties are desired for plant proteins, which is why similar bioprocessing of plant proteins using the same or other microbial extracellular proteases may promote the green protein transition. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. The number of publications in animal-based and plant-based dairy. The graph shows the number of publication per year in the Pubmed databased for the two search terms “animal dairy” and “plant dairy”.

indicates that we are facing knowledge gaps in the scientific space where we are early on the innovation curve in the case of plant dairy alternatives. Microbial fermented dairy alternatives have emerged as prototypes (Madsen et al., 2021a, 2021b) and further reviewed by Tangyu et al., 2019. However, there is no knowledge on the effect of extracellular proteolytic activity on dairy alternatives.

Therefore, we review the current knowledge on proteolytic microbes, which show extracellular proteolytic activity with plant proteins as substrates. The focus is on microbial species of LAB, yeast and filamentous fungi, which have a dominating history of use in food fermentation. Hereby, we aim to provide an overview of the application potentials of extracellular proteases targeting plant proteins related to the establish research field of microbial proteolysis of animal-based protein substrates, such as in the animal-based dairy fermentation.

2. Well known extracellular proteases from food microorganisms

Microorganisms perform proteolysis for the purpose of survival and growth, but the remaining peptides and amino acids can be useful to humans in food processing. This section explains how food microorganisms use extracellular proteases as part of their proteolytic system, as well as how well-known microbial extracellular proteases have been used in food development.

LAB play a prominent role in many food fermentations, and they dominate the research on the biochemistry of food fermentations. LAB are typically fastidious microorganisms with complex requirements that are auxotrophic for a range of amino acids. Several LAB possess proteolytic systems to satisfy their amino acid requirements. The proteolytic system in some strains includes a cell envelope proteinase (CEP), which allows extracellular proteins to be broken down into peptides short enough to be taken up by peptide transport systems. The CEP enzymes of LAB have been intensively researched, and the CEP of LAB species used in the dairy industry in particular have been thoroughly characterized. Roland Siezen has authored several papers and reviews on CEPs and subtilisins (Siezen, 1999; Siezen and Leunissen, 2008), and Ji, Ma, Xu, and Agyei have recently reviewed the biochemical features and biotechnological applications of CEPs from LAB (Ji et al., 2021). A modeled structure of a dairy associated CEP of *Lactococcus lactis* (Hansen and Marcatili, 2020) has led to a proposal for how this protease could use an entire casein micelle as substrate rather than individual protein molecules. The model has also led to novel hypotheses about the functions of the domains A, H, and W (Hansen and Marcatili, 2020). The current status is that the majority of research has been conducted on dairy-associated LAB strains, and casein has become the universal

substrate for protease research. However, this choice of substrate might lead to that proteases with alternative specificities are overlooked.

Fungi are another type of microorganism commonly used in food fermentation. Fungi have a proteolytic system based on proteases that can generate small peptides and amino acids for subsequent transport into the cell (Sabotić and Kos, 2012). Depending on the genus, different types of fungal proteases have been described. Aspartic proteases, also known as aspartic acid proteases, are one type of proteolytic enzymes synthesized by many filamentous fungi that can also be produced by some yeast species. Although these enzymes can be considered as virulence factors in fungal pathogenicity, they serve important functions in nutrition, health, and the food industry (Rao et al., 1998). Fungal aspartic proteases are synthesized as inactive precursors (zymogen) to protect against proteolysis. Changes in pH transform them into active enzymes with two aspartic residues at the catalytic site (Horimoto et al., 2009). The lengths of the mature proteins depend on each fungus, where the molecular weights range between 30 and 45 kDa (Mandujano-González et al., 2016). From the chemical point of view, the best activities of these proteases have been documented at low pH values (pH 3–4), and their specificity against aromatic or bulky amino acid residues on both sides of the peptide bond have been reported (Rao et al., 1998; Yegin et al., 2011). Aspartyl proteinases can be produced by *Aspergillus* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Rhizopus* spp., *Neurospora* spp., *Mucor* spp. and *Endothia* spp., and they can be categorized as pepsin-like and rennin-like enzymes (Sumantha et al., 2006). It is also known that some fungal genera, like *Aspergillus* or *Rhizopus*, can synthesized neutral or alkaline proteases, as it is the case of serine and metalloproteases. The group of serine proteases is characterized by having a serine residue in the active site, a low molecular mass (18–35 kDa) and an optimum working pH between 7 and 11 (Gupta et al., 2002). In contrast, metalloproteases constitute a group of diverse proteases that require divalent metal ions for being active (Rao et al., 1998).

Fungal proteases derived from GRAS [generally recognized as safe] microorganisms have traditionally been associated with food bioprocessing. Aspartic proteases play an important role in cheese-making industry, especially as milk-coagulating agents for cheese processing because of their high activity and stability at low pH values (Mandujano-González et al., 2016). The coagulant marked has been reported to be dominated by recombinant produced chymosin (55–60 %), fungal proteases (25–30 %), and the traditional animal rennets constituting the remaining share (10–20 %) (Andrén, 2021). Commercially available proteases used in the dairy industry for milk-clotting are mainly mucorpepsins produced by *Mucor pusillus*, *Mucor miehei* or recombinant mucorpepsins synthesized in *Aspergillus oryzae*, although many fungal species have been investigated as putative sources (e.g. *Endothia parasitica*, *Penicillium oxalicum*, *Saccharomycopsis fibuligera*). Moreover, other fungal proteases, such as neutral proteases from *Rhizopus oryzae* or *Aspergillus niger* proline-specific endoprotease, are used in cheese-making for debittering or accelerating cheese ripening times (Feijoo-Siota et al., 2014). Other extended applications of these enzymes are as clarification tools in the wine and beer industries. When beers or wines are not stable, haze appears, which may be caused by the interaction of proteins and polyphenols extracted from plant tissues (Lopez and Edens, 2005; Van Sluyter et al., 2015). Mamo and Assefa reviewed various fungal proteases that could be suitably used to degrade the turbidity complex (Mamo and Assefa, 2018). Acid proteinases produced by *S. fibuligera* combined with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* activity, have been effective in avoiding hazy beers, whereas aspergillopepsins I and II and *Botrytis cinerea* aspartic protease BcAP8 have successfully eliminated haze-forming proteins in white wines (Mamo and Assefa, 2018).

3. Crops and proteins of key importance in food production

Proteins derived from animals and plants have demonstrated extensive functionality in food technology, not only because of specific physicochemical properties such as emulsification, solubility, gelation

and flavor binding, but also because they provide nutritional values and bioactivities (Foegeding and Davis, 2011; Kinsella, 1976; Ma et al., 2022). Although the structure-functionality relationships of animal proteins have been extensively researched and used in food industry, the growing interest in plant proteins as a sustainable alternative has demonstrated challenges regarding their physicochemical and functional properties (Day, 2013; Ma et al., 2022; Qamar et al., 2020). Additionally some plant proteins are associated with toxicity and low nutritional value, among other things, which make them difficult to use in high-quality foods. Nevertheless, enzymatic hydrolysis of plant proteins can provide a way to overcome these challenges (Qamar et al., 2020;

Wouters et al., 2016).

This section is based on a review of the literature on the use of plant proteins as substrates for extracellular proteases from microorganism that have traditionally been used in food fermentation, as well as their roles in food product development and improvement. The focus is on LAB, yeast and filamentous fungal species and their extracellular proteases, which have been reported to target plant proteins.

Our main search is performed against the Scopus database using the keyword “lactic acid bacteria” in a parallel search with the keywords yeast, mold and “filamentous fungi”. The two parallel searches include the search terms proteolysis, protease, “proteolytic activity” or

Plant substrate	Properties of proteolysis	Proteolytic microbial species
Cereals <i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i> , <i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> , <i>Lactilactobacillus sakei</i> , <i>L. curvatus</i> , <i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i> , <i>Loigolactobacillus coryniformis</i> , <i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i> , <i>Weissella cibaria</i> , <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> , <i>P. acidilactici</i> <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Saccharomycopsis fibuligera</i> , <i>Torulasporea delbrueckii</i> <i>Rhizopus oryzae</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>A. oryzae</i> , <i>Mucor pusillus</i>		
Seeds <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i> , <i>Rhizopus oligosporus</i>		
Fruits <i>Oenococcus oeni</i> <i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> , <i>Metschnikowia pulcherrima</i> , <i>Candida utilis</i> <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Trichoderma viride</i> Mix fungal culture		
Legumes <i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i> , <i>Lacticaseibacillus casei</i> , <i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i> <i>Yarrowia lipolytica</i> <i>Rhizopus spp.</i> , <i>R. oryzae</i> , <i>R. oligosporus</i> , <i>Mucor flavus</i> , <i>M. wutungkiao</i> , <i>Aspergillus egyptiacus</i> , <i>Actinomucor elegans</i>		

Fig. 3. Plant substrates and derived properties for microbial proteolysis

Strains of the listed microbial species display extracellular proteolytic activity targeting plant proteins. Only plant proteins derived from the visualized plants have been studied as substrates for microbial extracellular proteases. The plant protein substrates excite as either a component of a food matrix or as pure protein. Properties of the proteolytic processes have been reported to increase (↑) or decrease (↓) functionalities of plant proteins. Plants are assigned a number if they are among the 15 highest ranked crops in Europe according to FAOSTAT, 2020. The current taxonomy of microbes is used, including the resent taxonomy reorganization of *Lactobacillus* genus (Zheng et al., 2020). Abbreviation: Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE). The majority of the plant figures are from BioRender.com.

proteinase. The search is performed within different groups of plants related to foods and plant-based food products including legume, pea, soy, lentil, bean, rice, cereal, sourdough, bread, seed, quinoa, flour, fruit, grape, berry, apple, wine, juice, seaweed, leaves, grass, vegetable, cabbage, root, potato, carrot, pumpkin, squash, tomato, kimchi, kraut, kvass, chutney, sauce, tea, nuts, and chili. Keyword filters related to microbial species, protein components, and protein hydrolysis have been used to refine the search results before manually assessment of the literature.

Our literature search reveals that certain groups of plants dominate the field of plant protein hydrolysis, which can be divided into four categories: cereals, seeds, fruits and legumes (Fig. 3). Other groups of plants such as nuts have not appeared based on our search criteria though we have conducted extra searches with more specifying keywords on plant sources e.g. almond.

3.1. Cereals

Cereals are cultivated grasses of the *Poaceae* family that provide edible grains with protein contents from 6 to 14 % (w/w) (Coda et al., 2012). The majority of the cereals produced, such as wheat, rye, rice, oat, maize and barley, are used for food or feed production. They are important protein sources in a variety of global diets (Wrigley, 2017). The proteins of cereals provide important properties to the food products and production processes because they aid in the milling, dough forming and baking processes (Schofield, 1994). Fermentation of cereal grains and flours has been proven to improve the sensory and nutritional value of cereal food products, as well as provide longer shelf-life and increase bio-activities (Nout and Motarjemi, 1997). However, there is still a controversy about how fermentation affects quality improvement as well as protein and amino acid availability (Blandino et al., 2003). The microbiology of fermented cereal-based products is complex since spontaneous and industrial fermentations involve mixed cultures.

In sourdough, LAB co-exist with yeast at a general ratio 100:1, where LAB strains can represent a variety of LAB species including *Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, *Levilactobacillus brevis*, *Limosilactobacillus pontis*, *Companilactobacillus paralimentarius*, *Furfurilactobacillus rossiae*, *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* and *Enterococcus faecalis* (Gänzle et al., 2008; Gobetti, 1998; Reale et al., 2021). *Lactobacilli* species are often present in sourdoughs and recognized for supporting sourdough development (Gänzle et al., 2008; Luti et al., 2020). Peptides of the native cereal proteins are released during the fermentation process as a result of a synergetic system of proteolytic activities. The acidifications of LAB activate endogenous cereal proteases as most of these proteases reach highest activity around pH 4–6 (Gänzle et al., 2008). The proteolysis of these endogenous cereals are known as the primary proteolytic step, which may be followed by microbial proteolysis in a secondary proteolytic step.

Peptides can be released from cereal proteins by chemically acidification (Coda et al., 2012), but LAB strains may contribute to additional protein and peptide degradation processes, increasing the functional properties of cereal proteins. *Lactobacilli* isolated from wheat sourdough can facilitate the release of antioxidant peptides in a wide range of cereals, including wheat, rye, rice, and oat doughs (Coda et al., 2012). Hereby, LAB strains demonstrate the ability to induce functionalities in some cereal proteins by allowing the release of bioactive peptides embedded in cereal proteins during fermentation.

LAB strains can degrade cereal proteins differently, which is connected to their extra- and intracellular proteolytic activities, among other LAB properties (Reale et al., 2021). These activities may be strain specific and not necessarily connected to species or isolated origin as observed in a clustering analysis of 131 *Lactobacilli* strains originating from sourdoughs (Galli et al., 2018). Strains of different LAB species have been shown to degrade cereal proteins such as gluten and gliadin (Reale et al., 2021; Stefańska et al., 2016). A plate based assay that uses wheat gluten or gliadin as the sole nitrogen source is effective in

detecting extracellular proteolytic activity of a *Levilactobacillus brevis* strain (Kunduhoglu and Hacıoglu, 2021). Clearing zones appear after bacterial growth when the plates are colored with the protein binding dye Coomassie Blue Brilliant, suggesting a quite efficient strain-specific protease activity. This elegant and simple plate assay excludes the contribution from endogenous proteases, but the enzymatic activity of the strain has not been elucidated further. The degradation of cereal proteins in e.g. sourdoughs appears often to be relatively modest. Peptide profiling of sourdough fermented wheat proteins reveals that the cereal proteins are cleaved at the surface and in their more flexible protein structures (Reale et al., 2021). Because even a modest degradation of the sourdough proteins may be enough to degrade epitopes, proteolytic LAB strains may facilitate the reduction of allergenicity of cereal proteins such as gluten (Stefańska et al., 2016). In other cases, epitopes can be targeted first by the protease activities of communities of LAB strains or communities of LAB strains combined with yeast or molds (Fu et al., 2021).

Protein hydrolysis can also occur during yeast fermentation in sourdoughs and alcoholic cereal-based beverages, with diverse effects on the final product depending on the cereal species and the yeast species. The degradation of allergens has been a major focus of wheat fermentation research. Although yeast species can have lower proteinase activity than LAB, some *S. cerevisiae* and *Torulaspora delbrueckii* strains present a synergistic effect with *P. acidilactici*, suggesting that co-cultures may accelerate protein degradation and reduce allergen content in the final wheat product (Fu et al., 2021, 2020). Furthermore, the combination of proteases from sourdough, LAB and fungal proteases has permitted for the elaboration of bread with reduced gluten content and with improved protein digestibility including higher bioavailability of essential amino acids (Rizzello et al., 2014). The protease utilization during long fermentation process has allowed for elimination of toxicity in wheat flour (Rizzello et al., 2007). Moreover, this interaction of LAB (*Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*) and fungi (*R. oryzae*) in other fermented cereals such as wholegrain oats has resulted in a higher content of soluble proteins and small peptides with ACE inhibitory activity, which could improve the nutritional and health profiles of wholegrain products (Wu et al., 2018).

Fungal proteases are also applied in the production of cereal based alcoholic beverages. As previously mentioned, proline-specific proteinases derived from *A. niger* are used to prevent haze formation in beers by degrading proline-rich peptides and proteins (Lopez and Edens, 2005; Van Schaick et al., 2021). Additionally, its combination with novel beer clarification tools appears to improve the colloidal stability and may present a solution for long-terms storage (Cimini and Moresi, 2018). Regarding other cereals, Asia has a great variety of rice wines, which are usually obtained by a simultaneous scarification and fermentation of steamed glutinous rice that has been inoculated with traditional starters, such as *Qus*, *Koji*, composed of a complex fungal and bacterial microbiota (Chen et al., 2021). These mixed starters are the most important driving force of sensorial development, but they pose a food safety risk, so specific fungal species have been selected for the elaboration of stable industrial starters (Zhang et al., 2019). Certain strains of *A. oryzae*, *A. niger* and *R. oryzae* species have been used as mixed cultures to enhance key flavor compounds as a result of their synergistic enzymatic activities. Interestingly, three types of proteases (acidic, alkaline and neutral proteases) are present in this multi-strain starter, but only neutral proteases increase protein decomposition efficiency by producing abundant short peptides, whereas acidic proteinases release the highest amounts of free amino acids (Yu et al., 2021). Fusel alcohols, which are characteristic flavor compounds in Asian fermented beverages, are derived from the amino acids catabolism, and their presence is associated to the strong proteolytic activity observed when *S. fibuligera* is used as the unique fungal starter. Nevertheless, a greater sensorial complexity is described when is combined with *A. oryzae* strains (Son et al., 2018).

3.2. Seeds

Seeds are embryonic plants, which are protected by outer covering. Nevertheless, as previously stated, seeds are not classified as fruits in terms of food technology. Raw seeds contain anti-nutritional factors and toxic compounds as chemical defenses against other living beings, which can be removed or reduced through technological treatments including fermentation (Gänzle, 2020). Fermentation of some seeds, such as cocoa and coffee beans, is essential for development of aroma precursors. Fermentation may also assist the removal of mucilaginous pulp, which draws out the drying process and leads to the development of spoilage microorganisms. Microbial enzymes from LAB, yeasts and other fungi play a major role during fermentation together with endogenous and native bean enzymes (Haile and Kang, 2019; Ho et al., 2014).

Filamentous fungi have been monitored during coffee and cocoa bean fermentation due to their negative effect during post-harvest processes. However, specific species have been proposed as new starter cultures based on their interesting proteolytic activity. *A. oryzae* is able to secrete a serine carboxypeptidase, which significantly enhances the sweet fruity notes of coffee by increasing the concentration of alkyl pyrazines. Because the production of these compounds is strongly related to amino acids degradation and aminoketone synthesis, it confirms that this protease has an important role in the improvement of the flavor profile of coffee (Murthy et al., 2019). Similar approach has been used in cocoa beans fermentation with an aspartic protease secreted by *A. oryzae*. In this case, the protease treatment of dry cocoa beans reduces the bitterness and increases the fruity and sweet flavors caused by elevated concentrations of pyrazines and acetates derived from amino acids (Murthy et al., 2020). Green coffee fermentation using *Rhizopus oligosporus* is also related to aroma modulation and a concentration increase of amino acids, especially alanine, glutamic acid and aspartic acid. Nonetheless, it seems that the change in aroma and amino acid levels is more of a combined effect of protein hydrolysis and *R. oligosporus* amino acid metabolism during fermentation than a specific impact of the fungal proteases (Lee et al., 2016).

3.3. Fruits

Fruit is defined in food technology as the edible part of a plant, tree, bush, or vine that contains the seeds and pulpy surrounded by an external tissue with a sweet, acid, or sour taste (World Health Organization and International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2003). Fruits are not associated with a high protein content, typically ranging between 0.1 and 1.5 % (Belitz et al., 2009). Most of the protein fraction is constituted of enzymes, and the fruit proteins may be limited to the non-edible parts of the fruit (Belitz et al., 2009; Cejudo-Bastante et al., 2022). Despite their low protein content, the proteins in some fruit-based foods are associated to food quality, shelf-life, and health benefits.

Proteins are of interest in grape juice and wine as precipitation of unstable proteins can result in haze formation over time, reducing shelf-life and quality of the juice and wine. Wine proteins are derived from both the grapes and the yeast in the wine. The hydrolysis of the peptide bonds by extracellular microbial proteases has been studied as a potential alternative to bentonite, which is commonly used to remove unstable proteins. Aspartic proteases (Aspergillopepsin I and II) produced by *A. niger* are active at wine pH and at temperatures where wine proteins remain unfolded. A combination of these proteases and a heat treatment (75 °C, 1 min) prior to fermentation has been proven to reduce nearly 90 % haze proteins in white wines (Marangon et al., 2012). Other proposed methods include using yeasts such as *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* and *Metschnikowia pulcherrima* during white must fermentation since some strains are able of secreting acidic proteases while the process is ongoing (Schlander et al., 2017). Prior to the fermentation, incubation of grape juices for 24–48 h with a protease produced by a *S. cerevisiae* strain reduces notably the presence of thermo-sensitive (thaumatin-like/27–28 kDa) and thermal-resistant

(endochitinases/34 kDa) proteins, confirming its potential application for hydrolyzing some of the proteins implicated in haze wine formation (Younes et al., 2013).

LAB may also hydrolyze grape proteins during wine fermentation, though the contribution is less elucidated. The LAB can reach population levels similar to yeast in wine fermentation and include the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Pediococcus* and *Oenococcus*. These LAB are key contributors in the malolactic fermentation of wine, which is a decarboxylation process converting tart-tasting malic acid into softer-tasting lactic acid. Interestingly, a genetic screening of 120 *Lactobacillus* strains from wine indicate that genes coding for PrtP-like serine proteases are not rare as they are represented in half of the tested strains and across *Lactobacillus* species (Mtsali et al., 2010). This study shows a potential of LAB as proteolytic operators in wine fermentation, but their actual role needs further examinations. The proteolytic effects of *Oenococcus oeni* strains with wine origin are best understood among LAB, and also here the proteolytic abilities appear to be strain specific (Cappello et al., 2010). Four *O. oeni* strains X₂L, L₂, m and ST secrete two extracellular proteases with activity against grape juice proteins. These proteases are produced at two different time points, corresponding to the early and late growth phases (Rollán et al., 1993). Protease activity of the LAB strains differs according to strain origin and protease type in terms of stability, optimal conditions and substrate specificity among other things (Rollán et al., 1995, 1993). Divalent cations affect the activities of the proteases differently, and the protease of the early growth phase appears to be more substrate selective than the protease of the late growth phase. The specific activity of the X₂L strain also show higher protease activity against the nitrogenous macromolecular fraction of red wine compare to white wine, which may be related to the lower protein concentration in red wine (Manca De Nadra et al., 1999). This observation is related to how nutrition and energy starvation can induce extracellular proteolytic activity in *O. oeni* X₂L (Rollán et al., 1998). The protease of this proteolytic strain has been partially purified and characterized as an aspartic, dimeric exoprotease whose activity for auto-claved grape juice protein substrate is abolished by Pepstatin A inhibition (Fariás and Manca de Nadra, 2000). The dimeric protease has a size of 33 kDa, and it has an optimum activity at pH 4.5 and 25 °C. Other *O. oeni* strains show extracellular protease activities, but their specificities against plant proteins stand unexamined (Folio et al., 2008; Remize et al., 2005).

Fruit-based by-products, such as seeds, peels and pulps residues, are also protein sources, which are normally discarded during industrial processing. Fermentation of citrus residues with a non-*Saccharomyces* yeast, *Candida utilis*, has increased the content of soluble proteins as well as essential and non-essential amino acids, especially leucine and phenylalanine, although protease activity is higher when a co-fermentation is carried out with *Bacillus subtilis*. Revalorization of citrus residue is complex since it requires the participation of several active enzymes such as pectinases, xylanases and cellulases. Enzymatic activities have been positively correlated with an increase in soluble protein content. Thus, after fermentation, the proteolytic activity is fostered, and the nutrient composition is improved (Huang et al., 2021). Filamentous fungi have also been tested for their ability to improve low-quality fruit by-products. The protein content increases in pineapple peels and olive cakes when they are fermented by *Trichoderma viride* and a mixed fungal cultures, respectively. In fact, the combination of different mold species allows for higher protein content (+95 %) than single specie fermentation (+15 %). Although it is assumed that this improvement is produced by the greater presence of proteases in mixed cultures, there is a lack of information regarding the determination and characterization of the specific enzymes implicated (Sabater et al., 2020).

3.4. Legumes

Legumes belong to the family *Fabaceae* and include among others

beans, soybeans, chickpeas, lentils, lupines and peanuts. This group of plants has both important agroecological and nutritional properties why legumes provide a basic pillar of human nutrition since ancient times (Martín-Cabrejas, 2019). Legumes form symbiotic relationships with nitrogen-fixing bacteria by which high-quality biomass of legumes can be obtained without requiring a large amount of nitrogen fertilizer. The protein contents of legumes are high and range between 20 and 35 % (w/w) of the total dry seeds (Martín-Cabrejas, 2019), which make them interesting as food ingredients as well as an important group of crops when changing to a more plant-based diet.

Among the legume proteins, soy proteins have particular interest as they are connected to allergenicity (Meinlschmidt et al., 2016b). Fermentation using *Lactobacillus helveticus* can significantly reduce the immunoreactivity of the soluble soy protein β -conglycinin (Meinlschmidt et al., 2016b). Meinlschmidt and coworkers suggest that the reduced immunoreactivity of β -conglycinin may be caused by a combination of acidic protein denaturation and strain specific proteolytic activity. The potential proteolytic activity of a *L. helveticus* strain has recently been elucidated, and this strain shows indeed specific degradation of several soluble soy proteins, including β -conglycinin, glycinin and albumin (Shirovani et al., 2021). The tested strains show different proteolytic activities for the total soy protein content, with proteolytic activity decreasing after 3 days of fermentation as measured by the release of free amino acids. However, the most proteolytic strains display only moderate activity and appear to preferentially target surface assessable cleavage sites or disordered protein regions. Other LAB and microbial strains also show relatively low proteolytic activity against legume proteins (Rizzello et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2018), whereas dairy LAB strains of *S. thermophilus* and *Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus* show substantial proteolytic activity against soy milk proteins as a dairy alternative (Hati et al., 2018). Mold species as *R. oryzae* and *Actinomyces elegans* do not show any effect on major soy allergens as glycinin and β -conglycinin when comparing protein patterns of untreated and fermented soy hydrolysates by SDS-PAGE. Although, their exoproteases can reduce the bitterness of the soy protein hydrolysates to make them more sensory attractive as food ingredient. Pretreatment of the soy protein with commercial microbial proteases permits the complete hydrolysis of the allergen β -conglycinin and the acidic subunit of glycinin by which subsequent fermentation with some molds may allow the production of low-allergen and sensory attractive soy hydrolysates (Meinlschmidt et al., 2016a, 2016b). Protease treatments can also increase soluble proteins in plant-based beverages (Manus et al., 2021; Verni et al., 2020). Prior to LAB fermentation, a lentil-based beverage uses a mixture of proteases derived primarily from plants to release peptides and free amino acids (Verni et al., 2020). Further proteolysis occurs during fermentation, but the contribution of LAB strain-derived extracellular proteases is unknown.

In some food matrices, the microbial growth potential depends on their extracellular proteolytic activities as recently observed for a proteolytic dairy *Streptococcus thermophilus* strain in soy milk (Boulay et al., 2020). Proteins involved in nitrogen metabolism predominate in numbers among the identified proteins in the proteomic profiling of *S. thermophilus* grown in soy milk as well as in cow milk. These predominating proteins include proteases and transporters of amino acid and peptides. Their abundance reflects the growth requirement for an extracellular nitrogen source. The extracellular protease PrtS plays an important role of the soy milk fermentation as mutations of this gene disturb the growth of this strain (Boulay et al., 2020). Supplementations of amino acid or low molecular casein hydrolysate do not stimulate growth of *S. thermophilus* in soy milk, but the PrtS mutant does restore growth at these conditions. In comparison to soy milk, the proteolytic strain still grows best in cow milk, where the highest lactate level is reached during fermentation (Boulay et al., 2020). The lactate production is not limited by the pH of the soy milk, which reaches the same level as for cow milk fermentation. Hereby, the growth of this strain may be limited by other factors than pH and proteolytic activity in soy milk.

Soy proteins, unlike most other plant proteins, have been used as a substrate for proteases discovery and characterization. In this respect, various molds associated with soy environments have emerged as an intriguing source of these enzymes, which are essential in the sensorial and technological development of soy-based foods. The bean curd product tofu can be fermented in a variety of ways to produce sufu, which is a soft cheese-like and highly flavored soybean-based product (He et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2020). Natural fermented tofu and tofu fermented with specific mold strains have a higher level of volatile compounds, which may be related to fungal protease activities. The volatile compounds can be linked to the enrichment of free amino acids produced during *A. elegans* fermentation of tofu (Yin et al., 2020). Interestingly, *A. elegans* secretes proteases and contains anabolic pathways for most of the amino acids. *Mucor flavus* produces a considerable amount of proteases at 15 °C during sufu production, and the rate of the proteolysis and amino-type nitrogen formation are comparable or even greater than that of other molds incubated at normal temperatures (Cheng et al., 2009). Fungal proteases may be used in combination with other enzymes to guide and control the flavor development of sufu production, though the proteolytic effects need to be investigated further (Cheng et al., 2009; He et al., 2022). In contrast, natto is traditional Japanese fermented whole soybean food, and natto fermented with a combination of *Mucor wutungkiao* and *B. subtilis* shows higher protease units than other mixtures, resulting in a significant better flavor. In addition, *M. wutungkiao* is able to reduce the content of various biogenic amines based on its ability of consume polyamines as a nitrogen source (Lan et al., 2020). The synergistic effect of diverse fungal species is also related to the biotransformation process of some soy byproducts like the okara from soy milk production. The yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica* can secrete proteases that hydrolyze proteins from the soy cell wall in the okara. The proteolysis may improve the action of carbohydrate-cleaving enzymes produced by *R. oligosporus* during fermentation besides releasing peptides and free amino acids. This microbial and enzymatic combination meliorates the nutritional and flavor properties of fermented okara, which could expand its valorization (Vong et al., 2018).

Because of the activity of microbial proteases, many small peptides are released during soy fermentation. Some of these peptides have demonstrated interesting therapeutic properties such as anti-hypertensive, antioxidant, antimicrobial. Traditional fermented soy products present small peptides with ACE inhibitory ability for treating high blood pressure and hypertension. Different studies highlight that the concentration of peptides with ACE inhibitory activity increases with fermentation and ripening time of soy products like douchi, sufu, maotofu and fermented soy milk (Sanjukta and Rai, 2016). Although the amino acid sequences of most soy foods fermented by molds have not been characterized, it is known that peptides with molecular weight less than 10 kDa are responsible for higher ACE inhibitory activity. Soy fermented with *Aspergillus egyptiacus* for producing douchi (fermented black soybeans) show a separated ACE inhibitor peptide fraction with an amino acid composition of phenylalanine, isoleucine and glycine in the ratio 1:2:5. (Lijun et al., 2003; Ma et al., 2013). In contrast, a different amino acid composition are found for ACE inhibitory peptides derived from soy milk fermented with the LAB species *Lactocaseibacillus casei* sub. *Pseudo Plantarum* (Vallabha and Tikku, 2014). Here, glutamic acid and threonine are highlighted to play an important role in ACE inhibition. Peptides derived from tempeh (fermented soybean cake-like product) produced with *Rhizopus* spp. or *R. oligosporus* have minor therapeutic effects. Antioxidant activity is found in peptides with aromatic amino acid and His residues that contribute to radical scavenging activity by stabilizing free radicals. Anticancer properties are associated to the peptide lunasin, which is not hydrolyzed by *R. oligosporus*, unlike other fungi use as starters, such as *A. oryzae* (Handoyo and Morita, 2006; Iwai et al., 2002).

4. Applications and challenges of plant protein hydrolysis

Microbial facilitated proteolysis is a well-known phenomenon in traditional fermented food products such as cheese, sausages, and cured ham, where the primary focus has been on the hydrolysis of animal-based proteins. This bioprocessing strategy of food appears to be transferable to plant proteins, but with other challenges due to the physicochemical differences of plant and animal-based proteins. Diverse LAB, yeast and mold species show extracellular protease activity that targets specific or various groups of plant proteins (Fig. 3). Their ability to ferment plants will facilitate the ongoing transition to a more plant-based diet (Fig. 1). Nonetheless, as previously discussed, the identification and characterization of the proteases involved in specific plant proteins hydrolysis, as well as their protein targets, require further and in-depth analysis (Table 1).

4.1. Proteolytic conditions in the fermented plant-based food matrix

Food fermentation provides a dynamic environment for proteolytic events, to which both the raw food material and microbial community contribute (Fig. 4). Additionally, the proteolytic output can be affected by physical and/or chemical treatment before, during or after the fermentation process.

The plant cell wall protects a large portion of plant proteins, such as storage proteins (Souza Cândido et al., 2011). Proteins from raw plant material can therefore be spatially protected from protease treatments. In contrast, proteins in some raw animal-based materials are not protected by cell walls such casein and whey proteins in milk. Lysis of plant cells may be required prior to proteolysis or as a step to speed up the fermentation process.

Different endogenous enzymes and inhibitors are common in a broad range of raw plant materials, and their activities can have a strong

Fig. 4. Parameters for microbial-based hydrolysis of plant proteins. Proteolytic parameters are outlined around the triangle and connected to three major groups: environment, substrate, and protease. These groups are highly interconnected, and together they define the reaction time and degree of proteolysis. Besides of external factors, plant and microbial material define the environmental matrix for proteolysis. The substrate and protease originate from plant material and microbial material, respectively, but they are also defined by their protein-protein interactions. Abbreviation: post-translational modifications (PTMs).

Table 1

Overview of extracellular microbial proteases that have been identified and characterized to target plant substrates.

Food substrates	Protease Type	E.C. Number	Species (strain)	Protein target	Role	Reference
Beer	Acid proline-specific endoprotease	3.4.21.26	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Proline rich peptides and proteins	Haze reduction	Lopez and Edens, 2005; Van Schaick et al., 2021
Rice wine	Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>A. niger</i> YF2; <i>Rhizopus oryzae</i> YF1; <i>Aspergillus oryzae</i> SU-16	-	Increment of free amino acids	Yu et al., 2021
	Neutral protease	3.4.24.-	<i>A. oryzae</i> SU-16	-	Increment of short peptides	
Coffee bean	Alkaline protease	3.4.21.-	<i>A. oryzae</i> SU-16	-	-	Murthy et al., 2019
	Serine-type carboxypeptidase	3.4.16.-	<i>A. oryzae</i> KX522630	-	Increment on the concentration of alkyl pyrazines	
Cocoa bean	Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>A. oryzae</i> CPO 025	-	Increment on the concentration of pyrazines and acetates	Murthy et al., 2020
Wine	Dimeric aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>Oenococcus oeni</i> X ₂ L	Peptides and glycosylated proteins from grape	LAB growth	Rollán et al., 1993; Manca De Nadra et al., 1999
	Aspergillopepsin-1	3.4.23.18	<i>A. niger</i> var. <i>macrosporus</i>	Chitinases and thaumatin-like proteins	Haze reduction	Marangon et al., 2012
	Aspergillopepsin-2	3.4.23.19	-	-	-	Schlander et al., 2017
	Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> 227	-	-	
	Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>Metschnikowia pulcherrima</i> 446	-	-	
Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> PIR1	Chitinases and thaumatin-like proteins	-	Younes et al., 2013	
Citrus pulp	Aspartic protease	3.4.23.-	<i>Candida utilis</i> GIM2.9	-	By-product revalorization	Huang et al., 2021
	Neutral protease	3.4.24.-	-	-	-	
Soybean	Serine protease (PrTH and PrTH2)	3.4.22.-	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i> LH88	β-conglycinin α subunit 1, β-conglycinin α' subunit, glycinin G1, and 2S albumin	Allergen reduction and volatile compound production	Shirotani et al., 2021
	Serine protease (PrTS)	3.4.21.110	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	-	Soy milk fermentation	Boulay et al., 2020

- Not specified.

impact on both the degree and specificity of the protein hydrolysis during fermentation. The endogenous enzymes, including proteases, are inactive in the native plant matrix, but a drop in pH activates some endogenous enzymes (Gänzle et al., 2008). An acidified environment may also activate aspartic proteases from both yeast and molds, as aspartic proteases have working pH optima in the range of 3–6 (Mandujano-González et al., 2016; Purushothaman et al., 2019). Because acidification is a part of LAB fermentation, it can be a strategy to achieve a peptide pool in a plant-based environment. The addition of microbial proteases with low pH optima may facilitate further hydrolysis of plant proteins by which availabilities of essential amino acids can be increased to support additional microbial fermentation with both proteolytic and non-proteolytic LAB and yeasts strains. Changes in the pH can also provide changes in plant protein solubility, which can make the proteins more or less assessable for proteolysis during acidifying fermentation (Gänzle et al., 2008; Shirovani et al., 2021). Soy protein has low solubility and forms gelation at acidic conditions, which may limiting their accessibility to proteolytic degradation during LAB fermentation (Shirovani et al., 2021). However, hydrolysis of soy proteins can increase their solubility by using aspartic proteases even at pH 4 (Purushothaman et al., 2019). Proteolytic properties have a potential to increase protein solubility, which interesting property could be used as a technological tool for stabilizing and produce complex plant-based products.

The contribution of endogenous enzymatic activities may also be removed by heating the raw plant material before fermentation. Thermal treatment may destabilize the endogenous enzymes as well as protease inhibitors along with other proteins in the food matrix. For example, when rice is steamed previous to a fungal fermentation to make rice wine, the content of free amino acids increases, which is related to flavor improvement (Yang et al., 2021). Therefore, heat treatment may change the structure of target plant proteins for proteolysis. A non-thermal protein pre-digestion can also be applied as it has been done in the sourdough matrix. The addition of fungal proteases (*A. niger* and *A. oryzae*) before lactic acid fermentation significantly reduces the gluten content of bread. The previous proteolysis may increase peptide availability for LAB and result in bread with higher digestibility, nutrition quality and similar structural and sensory features than non-treated dough (Rizzello et al., 2014).

Other intrinsic factors like the presence of ethanol after alcoholic fermentation led by *Saccharomyces* spp. may induce partial denaturation and precipitation of some of plant proteins (Nikolaidis and Moschakis, 2018). However, some oenological LAB secrete proteases that can increase the rate of amino acid liberation in presence of ethanol, implying that adapted microorganisms may generate adapted proteases for specific substrates conditions (Manca de Nadra et al., 2005). Other environmental changes can lead to structural changes in protein substrates, making them more or less accessible to proteases by which proteolytic activities may be increased or reduced.

Different groups of proteases require different salts, particularly divalent cation ions, in order to support their proteolytic activities. The structures of the CEPs are stabilized by the high Ca^{2+} level in milk by which they stay bound to the cell envelope of LAB (Exterkate and Altung, 1999). CEPs can be released in Ca^{2+} deficient media without losing their abilities to hydrolyze casein. Other cations have a direct impact on protein hydrolysis like Mg^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , which are essential for casein degradation (Guo et al., 2016). The extracellular microbial proteolytic activity targeting plant proteins also show to be differently affected by cations (Rollán et al., 1993). Sodium chloride stabilizes the aspartic protease of *A. niger* and protects the protease from thermal inactivation (Purushothaman et al., 2019). In contrast, increasing sodium chloride concentration reduces the unspecific proteolytic processes of rice koji derived *A. oryzae* in dairy fermentation, just like the salt reduces proteolytic activity of *Penicillium roqueforti* in blue cheese (Dank et al., 2021). Also, Ca^{2+} and Mn^{2+} salts can increase the activity of a neutral protease secreted by a *A. oryzae* strain isolated from fermented broad beans, whereas Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Zn^{2+} salts present an inhibitory effect

(Ao et al., 2018). Hereby, salts can be used to stabilize and adjust proteolytic activity in food developments (Fig. 4).

Protease expression can be quite energy consuming for microorganisms, as it is for the CEPs of LAB because CEPs are typically synthesized as pre-proteins of approximately 2000 amino acids (Ji et al., 2021). CEPs of LAB are only expressed when the environment is deficient in nitrogen sources and essential amino acids (Ji et al., 2021). In this way, the environment dictates the proteolytic activity by regulating the expression levels of some proteases besides the environmental impact on the structure and activity of the proteases and their substrates (Fig. 4).

4.2. Protein degradation in cross-over fermented and co-fermented food matrices

The microorganisms demonstrate strain-specific proteolytic abilities against plant-based proteins. Different strains of the same microbial species can have different proteolytic activities, and not all strains of the same microbial species do necessarily have extracellular protease activity (Mtshali et al., 2010). Dairy LAB strains indeed show strain-specific proteolytic patterns of their homologous extracellular proteases where CEPs from different *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *cremoris* strains both show differences in cleavage patterns as well as substrate selectivity for e.g. caseins. The underlying mechanism for these differences in proteolytic specificity and selectivity remains unclarified (Hansen and Marcatili, 2020). This highlights the challenges in predicting microbial proteolytic activity against target substrates, such as plant-based proteins, because their extracellular proteolytic potential cannot be linked to microbial species or isolated origin. One the other hand, this suggests that these food microbes contain a broad catalog of microbial extracellular protease variants, which could be used in combinations as part of a fermentation process and/or across food protein substrates.

The concept of cross-over fermentation has recently been defined where a microorganism of a traditional fermentation process is introduced to a new substrate and/or new microbial partner in a mixed culture (Dank et al., 2021). Although, this is not a novel concept, the technical term provides a good framework for studies focusing on non-traditional substrates for microbial-based proteolysis. LAB strains of well characterized dairy starters can target plant proteins using their extracellular enzymatic properties, as observed for *L. brevis* and *S. thermophilus* strains, which hydrolyze wheat and soy proteins, respectively (Boulay et al., 2020; Kunduhoglu and Hacıoglu, 2021). Probiotic supplement with three LAB strain has also been used to ferment plant protein-enriched beverages containing soy, hemp and/or rice protein concentrates (Manus et al., 2021). Although the protein degradation of the co-culture fermentation has not been directly linked to microbial extracellular proteases, the probiotic co-culture increases the soluble protein fraction and the levels of dipeptides and free amino acids in the plant-based beverages.

Several studies have also established that LAB strains originating from plants can utilize animal derived proteins as casein, which is a popular substrate in screenings of proteolytic food microbes. As an example, a plate-based screening assay has identified a *L. lactis* strain and an *Enterococcus hirae* strain as caseinolytic, and proteolytic potential of these microbes have been followed up by a second screening with different substrates (Pérez Borla et al., 2010). Among the caseinolytic LAB strains, only the *L. lactis* strain generates clearing halos on plates with other animal-based proteins, but also wheat gluten. Gluten is the only tested plant protein of this study why its ability to hydrolyze cabbage proteins is unexplored. This work shows that extracellular proteases of LAB can exhibit varied substrate selectivity across and between plant and animal food matrices, implying that proteolytic microbes may bring unique features in future cross-over fermentations. A similar selection approach is provided in Ben-Harb et al., 2019 study, which creates a mixed plant-based product (e.g., 50 % milk – 50 % pea protein)

and a pure pea protein emulsion. However, the proteolytic activity of caseinolytic *L. lactis* strain remains selectivity against the substrates reported (Pérez Borla et al., 2010). The strong substrate selectivity of some extracellular LAB proteases raised the question of whether proteolytic screenings overlook other, possibly novel, proteolytic activity by using casein as a substrate. One way to circumvent this concern is to test non-caseinolytic strains against other substrates, as Pérez Borla et al., 2010 did by using random checks to reduce the uncertainties for overlooking targeting proteolytic bacteria.

Another aspect of the plant protein degradation is the occurrence of posttranslational modifications (Fig. 4). Wheat germ agglutinin, a cereal lectin protein, have 16 disulfide bridges to stabilize its monomeric structure. This protein stability can be challenged by microbes with glutathione reductases, which can change the redox potential during

fermentation (Rojas Tovar and Gänzle, 2021). Transglutaminase activity of microbes may also cross-link different cereal proteins by isopeptide bonds during sourdough fermentation. This create structural networks with dough structure qualities, but it can also enhance the formation of volatile compounds (Scarnato et al., 2016). However, it is unclear how these and other posttranslational modifications influence on proteolytic processes in fermentation where proteases of the microbial community and plant matrix may synergetic contribute to plant protein degradation.

A few studies have looked into the synergetic proteolytic effects between microbes of co-cultures, which can promote proteolytic activity in plant fermentation (Fu et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018). Fermentations with co-cultures result in complex changes to the food matrix including the proteins as a result of microbial competition and synergetic activities

Fig. 5. Synergistic effects of proteolytic food microbes in plant fermentation

Principal synergistic effects (arrows) are observed in food fermented with co-cultures. The figure center depicts the main compounds derived from proteolytic activity of plant proteins, including peptides and amino acids (aa). The synergetic effects of the microbial proteases (scissors) may further facilitate the proteolytic process, but degradation of carbohydrates (pentagon and hexagon) may also facilitate microbial proteolysis of plant proteins. The data reviewed in this article support interactions between lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and fungi based on the only plant fermented foods that have been studied, such as sourdoughs, wines, and soy products, as well as products resulting from proteolytic activity. The figure does not include synergetic contributions of endogenous enzymes within the plant matrix.

(Fig. 5). In rich nutrient environments such as sourdoughs or grape juices, LAB and yeast growth are stimulated by the lack of competition for the nitrogen source and the excretion of amino acids, peptides and micronutrients by the yeasts. Yeast proteases can release some essential amino acids such as valine and isoleucine and small peptides that allow specific LAB species to grow (Gobbetti et al., 1994). Because of the accelerated metabolism of LAB, monosaccharides are easily available and permit yeasts to uptake glucose, which induce the secretion of amino acids from the cell. The efficient use of these peptides and amino acids produced by yeast provides a competitive advantage for the LAB, which contribute to the stability of the fermented food (Gobbetti, 1998). Hereby, growth performance of microbes can be supported by a complex synergetic interplay in a microbial consortia. A *L. plantarum* strain isolated from cereal has improved growth performance when co-cultured with *R. oryzae* in whole-grain oat fermentation (Wu et al., 2018). The improved growth may be related to protein metabolic processes as the co-inoculated fermentation provides higher protein solubility, degree of hydrolysate and content of smaller peptides. RNA-sequencing shows transcriptomic changes of *P. acidilactici* when co-cultures with the yeast species *S. cerevisiae* and *T. delbrueckii* (Fu et al., 2021). These changes indicate that yeast can enhance the protein metabolism of *P. acidilactici*, which correlates with accelerated protein degradation and reduce immunoreactivity of insoluble wheat proteins. Furthermore, the proteolytic activity of *Y. lipolytica* might have made carbohydrates, such as cellulose and hemicellulose, more accessible to *R. oligosporus* carbohydrases. These carbohydrate-cleaving enzymes would transform insoluble dietary fibers into disaccharides and monosaccharides, which could then be further catabolized to support microbial growth (Vong et al., 2018). This synergistic metabolism between *Y. lipolytica* and *R. oligosporus* may be responsible for the majority of the conversion from non-digestible polysaccharides to soluble fibers, which can improve the nutritional value of some plant-based foods.

4.3. Hydrolyzing plant proteins in food product developments

Endogenous proteases found in plant-based matrices may provide enough free peptides and amino acids for microbial growth, which is why these proteases enable development of fermented food products without the use of microbial extracellular proteases (Fig. 4). Therefore, traditionally plant-based food products and spontaneously fermented plant-matrixes are not necessarily sources of microbes with extracellular proteases, but examples of microbes with plant origin have been identified with extracellular protease activity (Cappello et al., 2010; Fu et al., 2021; Reale et al., 2021; Shirotani et al., 2021). Microbial assisted proteolysis can further enhanced proteolysis, which may increase protein digestibility (Rizzello et al., 2019). Hereby, the microbial proteases

may expand the functional catalog of proteolysis by introducing potential increased and modified cleavage events. Monocultures of LAB used as dairy starter cultures perform not as well in soy milk compared to cow milk (Hati et al., 2018), but the proteolytic capacity is not the limiting growth factor for the PrtP containing *S. thermophilus* strain (Boulay et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the extracellular proteolytic capacity of *S. thermophilus* is directly linked to its growth potential in soy milk (Boulay et al., 2020). The soy proteins are not fully degraded but just enough to support growth. Among 276 LAB strains, the *S. thermophilus* strain acidifies soy milk most efficiently (Harlé et al., 2020); whether this difference is related to their extracellular proteolytic potential is unknown. However, microbial assisted proteolysis of plant-based proteins can be required for some strains and support plant protein functionalities, which is why food microbes with extracellular proteases have the potential to facilitated plant-based food development in a similarly way that they are used in animal-based foods (Fig. 1).

To link the protease with the microbial proteolytic capacity, a specific extracellular protease has been mutated in a *S. thermophilus* strain. Such research studies are uncommon, leaving a knowledge gap in our understanding of microbial-assisted proteolysis of plant proteins (Fig. 6). The proteolytic activities of microbes have been studied in diverse plant-based food matrixes (Fig. 3) using different methods, the most prominent of which are growth experiments (Fig. 6). Spectrometric assays such as enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and o-phthalaldehyde (OPA) assay are frequently applied to quantify proteolytic processes of plant-based substrates. Proteolysis is also frequently quantified by measuring levels of free amino acids with liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) or by considering the substrate degradation patterns by sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). The qualities of plant-based protein substrate hydrolysis is less frequently assessed. Peptide profiling has provided valuable insights into the moderate cleavage of plant-based substrates, as the microbial extracellular proteases mostly cleaved the surface assessable surface areas and intrinsic disorder regions of their target substrates (Reale et al., 2021; Shirotani et al., 2021). Microbial proteases with plant protein targets have been studied with either bioinformatics or biochemical approaches (Fig. 6). Genome mining and also polymerase chain reaction (PCR) show the presence of plant origin homologs of proteases used in dairy while SDS-PAGE has characterized proteases in proteolytic fractions. Future studies are requested to bridge the knowledge gap between proteolysis and the proteases to match, for example, by supplementing proteolytic studies with bioinformatics searches and characterization of potential microbial extracellular proteases. Extracellular proteolytic activities of LAB strains are not well characterized with a few known extracellular proteases with plant protein targets (Table 1), as observed for *O. oeni* with different

Fig. 6. A methodological gap in the study of microbial extracellular proteolysis of plant proteins. The schematic illustration shows some methods, which are applied to study proteolysis of plant proteins using microbial extracellular protease. The methods are listed in decreasing order of relative use from left to right. The frequency is related to the purpose of the methods, which is to characterize proteolysis as a process or the protease itself. The connection between the proteolytic process and the protease is rare, leaving a gap illustrated by the “broken” triangle. Sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) has been used to study proteolytic processes and characterize proteases by focusing on the substrate or the protease, respectively. Other abbreviations: liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), Polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

suggested proteases in wine fermentation (Section 3.3). Extracellular protease activities of yeast and filamentous fungi are better characterized since there appear to be few species and protease types that are useful in plant protein hydrolysis (Table 1). Nonetheless, more LAB species can be selected as candidates for proteolytic activity targeting plant proteins since it seems that studies with molds commonly focus on the well-known species (e.g. *A. oryzae*, *R. oryzae*, and *A. niger*), which is more notorious in the case of yeasts (e.g. *S. cerevisiae* and *S. fibuligera*). Future studies may focus on the proteolytic potential of other non-investigated fungal species as well as non-conventional yeasts. However, food fermentation procedures are associated with potential health risks, which is why microorganisms and their metabolites should be handled with caution in both spontaneous fermentation and innovative co-cultures, as well as cross-over fermentation with applied starter cultures (Capozzi et al., 2017, 2020; Verni et al., 2020).

Characterization of microbial proteases is required to predict and steer proteolytic events in food developments in order to obtain target protein functionalities. Plant proteins are generally moderately hydrolyzed, leaving the hydrolysate with larger peptide fragments and the majority of proteins in their native states (e.g. A. Reale et al., 2021; Shirotani et al., 2021). Defining the optimal conditions for a target microbial driven proteolysis are challenging where both substrate, protease and microorganism must tolerate the fermentation conditions, which can change over time (Fig. 4). Extracellular microbial proteolysis has only been analyzed in a relatively few plant-based protein sources, which only represent four groups of crops. These groups are only represented by a few crops of which six are among the 15 major crops in Europe (FAOSTAT, 2020) (Fig. 3). Other crops have not, to our knowledge, been studied in relation to extracellular microbial proteolysis, despite the fact that major crops are clearly missing. Together with wheat and sugar beets, maize and potatoes are two of Europe's four major crops. Maize is a cereal with 8–12 % (w/w) protein of its kernel. These proteins embed bioactive peptides with antioxidant, antihypertensive, anticancer and antimicrobial properties that are primarily released through Alcalase hydrolysis (Díaz-Gómez et al., 2017). Antioxidant activity has not been increased by using a specific combination of different *Lactobacilli* strains, which release antioxidant peptides from other cereal proteins (Coda et al., 2012). This strain specific proteolytic activity of microbes highlights the importance for further searching of proteolytic microbes, which can provide proteases with desired proteolytic activities against diverse plant protein substrates. Potato is a root containing 1–2 % (w/w) proteins, and it is essential as core component in diet and in industrial starch production. Potato protein accumulated in industrial side streams provides a valuable source for bioactive peptides with emulsifying and antioxidant activities, which activities are verified using corresponding synthetic peptides (García-Moreno et al., 2020b). Hereby, plant proteins of diverse plant groups may embed valuable bioactive peptides with important functionalities for food developments. The release of bioactive peptides require specific proteolytic cleavage where food microbes with modest extracellular protease activity may be ideal for their release. The specific cleavage is challenged by the protease selectivity and specificity which determined if and where it cleavages its substrate. Therefore, novel extracellular proteases and protease composition are required to fully explore the proteolytic potential of LAB, yeast and molds.

5. Conclusion

Versatile extracellular proteases are found in traditionally applied food microbes of LAB, yeast and mold species, the origins of which cover a wide range of animal- and plant-based food matrixes. The protease activity is specific for the microbial strain and not to the species or the isolated origin of the microbe. This indicates that these food microbes have a diverse set of extracellular proteases, which can be used on substrates across food matrixes. Extracellular proteases of LAB, yeast and mold have only been shown to target plant proteins from four crop

groups, with a very limited representation of plants within each group. The low representation of plant substrates in proteolytic studies is a challenge. Although casein is the most commonly used substrate for proteolytic screenings, this approach runs the risk of overlooking novel proteolytic activities because extracellular proteases can display versatile substrate selectivity across and between plant and animal proteins. We are facing a knowledge gap where the proteolytic process is rarely connected to the protease itself, and vice versa. This knowledge gap makes it challenging to predict and steer the proteolytic capacity of microbes. However, the hydrolysis of the four plant groups reflects a promising application potential for developing plant-based foods as dairy alternatives. Microbial proteolysis can improve plant protein digestibility, just as their extracellular proteolysis can target protein-based off-flavors, anti-nutritional factors, toxins, and allergens. Extracellular proteolysis of plant proteins appears to be quite modest, which may explain why the desired properties of the plant protein hydrolysate may be facilitated by a complex synergetic interplay of microbes in co-cultures. Specific cleavage of proteolytic microbes may also release bioactive peptides, which provide valuable functions to foods. Hereby, the search for plant-targeting proteolytic microbes is not limited to supporting microbial growth in plant fermentation, where endogenous proteases can cover the amino acid requirements for some microbes. The vision is to explore and utilize the full proteolytic potential of food microbes in order to facilitate the development of high quality food products as part of the ongoing transition to a plant-based diet.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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References

- Aiking, H., de Boer, J., 2020. The next protein transition. Trends Food Sci. Technol. 105, 515–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2018.07.008>.
- Andrn, A., 2021. Milk-clotting enzymes. In: Kelly, A.L., Larsen, L.B. (Eds.), Agents of Change: Enzymes in Milk and Dairy Products. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 349–362. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-55482-8_14.
- Ao, X., Lin, Yu, X., Wu, D., Tao, Li, C., Zhang, T., Liu, S., Liang, Chen, S., Juan, He, L., Zhou, K., Zou, L., Kou, 2018. Purification and characterization of neutral protease from *Aspergillus oryzae* Y1 isolated from naturally fermented broad beans. AMB Express 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-018-0611-6>.
- Belitz, H.D., Grosch, W., Schieberle, P., 2009. Fruits and fruit products. In: Food Chemistry. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 807–859. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69934-7>.
- Ben-Harb, S., Saint-Eve, A., Panouille, M., Souchon, I., Bonnarme, P., Dugat-Bony, E., Irlinger, F., 2019. Design of microbial consortia for the fermentation of pea-protein-enriched emulsions. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 293, 124–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2019.01.012>.
- Blandino, A., Al-Aseeri, M.E., Pandiella, S.S., Cantero, D., Webb, C., 2003. Cereal-based fermented foods and beverages. Food Res. Int. 36, 527–543. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969\(03\)00009-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-9969(03)00009-7).
- Boulay, M., Al Haddad, M., Rul, F., 2020. Streptococcus thermophilus growth in soya milk: sucrose consumption, nitrogen metabolism, soya protein hydrolysis and role of the cell-wall protease PrtS. Int. J. Food Microbiol. 335, 108903 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2020.108903>.
- Bourdichon, F., Casaregola, S., Farrokhi, C., Frisvad, J.C., Gerds, M.L., Hammes, W.P., Harnett, J., Huys, G., Laulund, S., Ouweland, A., Powell, I.B., Prajapati, J.B., Seto, Y., Ter Schure, E., Van Boven, A., Vankerckhoven, V., Zgodia, A., Tuijtelaars, S., Hansen, E.B., 2012. Food fermentations: microorganisms with technological

- beneficial use. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 154, 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodmicro.2011.12.030>.
- Capozzi, V., Fragasso, M., Romaniello, R., Berbegal, C., Russo, P., Spano, G., 2017. Spontaneous food fermentations and potential risks for human health. *Fermentation* 3, 49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation3040049>.
- Capozzi, V., Fragasso, M., Russo, P., 2020. Microbiological safety and the management of microbial resources in artisanal foods and beverages: the need for a transdisciplinary assessment to conciliate actual trends and risks avoidance. *Microorganisms* 8, 306. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8020306>.
- Cappello, M.S., Zapparoli, G., Stefani, D., Logrieco, A., 2010. Molecular and biochemical diversity of oenococcus oeni strains isolated during spontaneous malolactic fermentation of malvasia nera wine. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 33, 461–467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.syapm.2010.09.003>.
- Cejudo-Bastante, M.J., Oliva-Sobrado, M., González-Miret, M.L., Heredia, F.J., 2022. Optimisation of the methodology for obtaining enzymatic protein hydrolysates from an industrial grape seed meal residue. *Food Chem.* 370, 131078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.131078>.
- Chen, G.M., Huang, Z.R., Wu, L., Wu, Q., Guo, W.L., Zhao, W.H., Liu, B., Zhang, W., Rao, P.F., Lv, X.C., Ni, L., Sun, J.Y., Sun, B.G., 2021. Microbial diversity and flavor of chinese rice wine (Huangjiu): an overview of current research and future prospects. *Curr. Opin. Food Sci.* 42, 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2021.02.017>.
- Cheng, Y.Q., Hu, Q., Li, L., Te, Saito, M., Yin, L.J., 2009. Production of sufu, a traditional chinese fermented soybean food, by fermentation with *Mucor flavus* at low temperature. *Food Sci. Technol. Res.* 15, 347–352. <https://doi.org/10.3136/fstr.15.347>.
- Cimini, A., Moresi, M., 2018. Combined enzymatic and crossflow microfiltration process to assure the colloidal stability of beer. *LWT* 90, 132–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.12.008>.
- Coda, R., Rizzello, C.G., Pinto, D., Gobbetti, M., 2012. Selected lactic acid bacteria synthesize antioxidant peptides during sourdough fermentation of cereal flours. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 78, 1087–1096. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.06837-11>.
- Dank, A., van Mastrigt, O., Yang, Z., Dinesh, V.M., Lillevang, S.K., Weij, C., Smid, E.J., 2021. The cross-over fermentation concept and its application in a novel food product: the dairy miso case study. *LWT* 142, 111041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111041>.
- Day, L., 2013. Proteins from land plants - potential resources for human nutrition and food security. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 32, 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2013.05.005>.
- Díaz-Gómez, J.L., Castorena-Torres, F., Preciado-Ortiz, R.E., García-Lara, S., 2017. Anti-cancer activity of maize bioactive peptides. *Front. Chem.* 5, 44. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2017.00044>.
- Exterkate, F.A., Altling, A.C., 1999. Role of calcium in activity and stability of the lactococcus lactis cell envelope proteinase. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 65, 1390–1396. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.65.4.1390-1396.1999>.
- FAOSTAT, 2020. FAOSTAT [WWW document]. URL: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>. (Accessed 28 February 2022).
- Fariñas, M.E., Manca de Nadra, M.C., 2000. Purification and partial characterization of oenococcus oeni exoprotease. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 185, 263–266. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6968.2000.tb09072.x>.
- Fejoo-Siota, L., Blasco, L., Rodríguez-Rama, J.L., Barros-Velázquez, J., Miguel, T.D., Sánchez-Pérez, A., Villa, T.G., 2014. Recent patents on microbial proteases for the dairy industry. *Recent Adv. DNA Gene Seq.* 8, 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.2174/2352092208666141013231720>.
- Foegeding, E.A., Davis, J.P., 2011. Food protein functionality: a comprehensive approach. *Food Hydrocoll.* 25, 1853–1864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2011.05.008>.
- Folio, P., Ritt, J.F., Alexandre, H., Remize, F., 2008. Characterization of EprA, a major extracellular protein of oenococcus oeni with protease activity. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 127, 26–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.IJFOODMICRO.2008.05.039>.
- Fu, W., Xue, W., Liu, C., Tian, Y., Zhang, K., Zhu, Z., 2020. Screening of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts from sourdough as starter cultures for reduced allergenicity wheat products. *Foods* 9, 751. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9060751>.
- Fu, W., Liu, C., Meng, X., Tao, S., Xue, W., 2021. Co-culture fermentation of pediococcus acidilactici XZ31 and yeast for enhanced degradation of wheat allergens. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 347, 109190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodmicro.2021.109190>.
- Galli, V., Mazzoli, L., Luti, S., Venturi, M., Guerrini, S., Paoli, P., Vincenzini, M., Granchi, L., Pazzagli, L., 2018. Effect of selected strains of lactobacilli on the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of sourdough. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 286, 55–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.IJFOODMICRO.2018.07.018>.
- Gänzle, M.G., 2020. Food fermentations for improved digestibility of plant foods – an essential ex situ digestion step in agricultural societies? *Curr. Opin. Food Sci.* 32, 124–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2020.04.002>.
- Gänzle, M., 2022. The periodic table of fermented foods: limitations and opportunities. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 106, 2815–2826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-022-11909-y>.
- Gänzle, M.G., Loponen, J., Gobbetti, M., 2008. Proteolysis in sourdough fermentations: mechanisms and potential for improved bread quality. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 19, 513–521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2008.04.002>.
- García-Moreno, P.J., Gregersen, S., Nedamani, E.R., Olsen, T.H., Marcatili, P., Overgaard, M.T., Andersen, M.L., Hansen, E.B., Jacobsen, C., 2020a. Identification of emulsifier potato peptides by bioinformatics: application to omega-3 delivery emulsions and release from potato industry side streams. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 690. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-57229-6>.
- García-Moreno, P.J., Jacobsen, C., Marcatili, P., Gregersen, S., Overgaard, M.T., Andersen, M.L., Sørensen, A.-D.M., Hansen, E.B., 2020b. Emulsifying peptides from potato protein predicted by bioinformatics: stabilization of fish oil-in-water emulsions. *Food Hydrocoll.* 101, 105529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2019.105529>.
- Gobbetti, M., 1998. The sourdough microflora: interactions of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 9, 267–274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244\(98\)00053-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244(98)00053-3).
- Gobbetti, M., Corsetti, A., Rossi, J., 1994. The sourdough microflora. Interactions between lactic acid bacteria and yeasts: metabolism of carbohydrates. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 41, 456–460. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00939035>.
- Guo, T., Ouyang, X., Xin, Y., Wang, Y., Zhang, S., Kong, J., 2016. Characterization of a new cell envelope proteinase PrtP from lactobacillus rhamnosus CGMCC11055. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 64, 6985–6992. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.6b03379>.
- Gupta, R., Beg, Q., Lorenz, P., 2002. Bacterial alkaline proteases: molecular approaches and industrial applications. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 59, 15–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-002-0975-y>.
- Haile, M., Kang, W.H., 2019. The role of microbes in coffee fermentation and their impact on coffee quality. *J. Food Qual.* 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4836709>.
- Handoyo, T., Morita, N., 2006. Structural and functional properties of fermented soybean (Tempeh) by using rhizopus oligosporus. *Int. J. Food Prop.* 9, 347–355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942910500224746>.
- Hansen, E.B., Marcatili, P., 2020. Modeled structure of the cell envelope proteinase of lactococcus lactis. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.613986>.
- Harlé, O., Falentin, H., Niay, J., Valence, F., Courselaud, C., Chuat, V., Maillard, M.B., Guédon, E., Deutsch, S.M., Thierry, A., 2020. Diversity of the metabolic profiles of a broad range of lactic acid bacteria in soy juice fermentation. *Food Microbiol.* 89, 103410. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.FM.2019.103410>.
- Hati, S., Patel, N., Mandal, S., 2018. Comparative growth behaviour and biofunctionality of lactic acid bacteria during fermentation of soy milk and bovine milk. *Probiotics Antimicrob. Proteins* 10, 277–283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12602-017-9279-5>.
- He, W., Chen, Z., Chung, H.Y., 2022. Dynamic correlations between major enzymatic activities, physicochemical properties and targeted volatile compounds in naturally fermented plain sufu during production. *Food Chem.* 378, 131988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2021.131988>.
- Ho, V.T.T., Zhao, J., Fleet, G., 2014. Yeasts are essential for cocoa bean fermentation. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 174, 72–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodmicro.2013.12.014>.
- Horimoto, Y., Dee, D.R., Yada, R.Y., 2009. Multifunctional aspartic peptidase proteasomes. *New Biotechnol.* 25, 318–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2009.03.010>.
- Huang, W.Q., Hu, X., Zeng, J.R., Tian, X.F., Wu, Z.Q., 2021. Changing the nutrient composition and enhancing the hydrolytic enzyme activity of citrus pulp residue by cofermentation with *Candida utilis* and *Bacillus subtilis*. *Process Biochem.* 107, 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2021.05.005>.
- Iwai, K., Nakaya, N., Kawasaki, Y., Matsue, H., 2002. Antioxidative functions of natto, a kind of fermented soybeans: effect on LDL oxidation and lipid metabolism in cholesterol-fed rats. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 50, 3597–3601. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0117199>.
- Ji, D., Ma, J., Xu, M., Agyei, D., 2021. Cell-envelope proteinases from lactic acid bacteria: biochemical features and biotechnological applications. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 20, 369–400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12676>.
- Joshi, R., Sharma, V., Kula, A., 2018. Fermentation technology: current status and future prospects. In: Kula, A., Sharma, V. (Eds.), *Principles and Applications of Fermentation Technology*. Scrivener Publishing LLC. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119460381.ch1>.
- Kinsella, J.E., 1976. Functional properties of proteins in foods: a survey. *CRC Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 7, 219–280. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408397609527208>.
- Kunduhoglu, B., Hacıoglu, S., 2021. Probiotic potential and gluten hydrolysis activity of lactobacillus brevis KT16-2. *Probiotics Antimicrob. Proteins* 13, 720–733. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12602-020-09723-x>.
- Lan, G., Li, C., He, L., Zeng, X., Zhu, Q., 2020. Effects of different strains and fermentation method on natto-kinase activity, biogenic amines, and sensory characteristics of natto. *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 57, 4414–4423. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-020-04478-3>.
- Lee, L.W., Cheong, M.W., Curran, P., Yu, B., Liu, S.Q., 2016. Modulation of coffee aroma via the fermentation of green coffee beans with *Rhizopus oligosporus*: I. Green coffee. *Food Chem.* 211, 916–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.05.076>.
- Lijun, W., Saito, M., Tatsumi, E., Lite, L.I., 2003. Antioxidative and angiotensin I-converting enzymes inhibitory activities of sufu (Fermented Tofu) extracts. *Japan Agric. Res. Q.* 37, 129–132. <https://doi.org/10.6090/jarq.37.129>.
- Lopez, M., Edens, L., 2005. Effective prevention of chill-haze in beer using an acid proline-specific endoprotease from aspergillus niger. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53, 7944–7949. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0506535>.
- Luti, S., Mazzoli, L., Ramazzotti, M., Galli, V., Venturi, M., Marino, G., Lehmann, M., Guerrini, S., Granchi, L., Paoli, P., Pazzagli, L., 2020. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of sourdoughs containing selected lactobacilli strains are retained in breads. *Food Chem.* 322, 126710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.126710>.
- Ma, Y., Cheng, Y., Yin, L., Wang, J., Li, L., 2013. Effects of processing and NaCl on angiotensin I-converting enzyme inhibitory activity and γ -aminobutyric acid content during sufu manufacturing. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 6, 1782–1789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-012-0852-3>.
- Ma, K.K., Greis, M., Lu, J., Nolden, A.A., McClements, D.J., Kinchla, A.J., 2022. Functional performance of plant proteins. *Foods* 11, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11040594>.

- Madsen, S.K., Priess, C., Wätjen, A.P., Özmerih, S., Mohammadifar, M.A., Heiner Bang-Berthelsen, C., 2021a. Development of a yoghurt alternative, based on plant-adapted lactic acid bacteria, soy drink and the liquid fraction of brewers' spent grain. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 368, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnab093>.
- Madsen, S.K., Thulesen, E.T., Mohammadifar, M.A., Bang-Berthelsen, C.H., 2021b. Chufa drink: potential in developing a new plant-based fermented dessert. *Foods* 10, 3010. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10123010>.
- Mamo, J., Assefa, F., 2018. The role of microbial aspartic protease enzyme in food and beverage industries. *J. Food Qual.* 2018 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7957269>.
- Manca De Nadra, M.C., Fariás, M.E., Moreno-Arribas, V., Pueyo, E., Polo, M.C., 1999. A proteolytic effect of oenococcus oeni on the nitrogenous macromolecular fraction of red wine. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 174, 41–47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1097\(99\)00119-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1097(99)00119-6).
- Manca de Nadra, M.C., Fariás, M.E., Pueyo, E., Polo, M.C., 2005. Protease activity of oenococcus oeni viable cells on red wine nitrogenous macromolecular fraction in presence of SO₂ and ethanol. *Food Control* 16, 851–854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCONT.2004.06.027>.
- Mandujano-González, V., Villa-Tanaca, L., Anducho-Reyes, M.A., Mercado-Flores, Y., 2016. Aspartil-proteasas secretadas por hongos: revisión. *Rev. Iberoam. Micol.* 33, 76–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riam.2015.10.003>.
- Manus, J., Millette, M., Uscanga, B.R.A., Salmieri, S., Maherani, B., Lacroix, M., 2021. In vitro protein digestibility and physico-chemical properties of lactic acid bacteria fermented beverages enriched with plant proteins. *J. Food Sci.* 86, 4172–4182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.15859>.
- Marangon, M., Van Sluyter, S.C., Robinson, E.M.C., Muhlack, R.A., Holt, H.E., Haynes, P. A., Godden, P.W., Smith, P.A., Waters, E.J., 2012. Degradation of white wine haze proteins by aspergillopepsin i and II during juice flash pasteurization. *Food Chem.* 135, 1157–1165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2012.05.042>.
- Martín-Cabrejas, M.A., 2019. Legumes: an overview. In: Martín-Cabrejas, M.A. (Ed.), *Legumes: Nutritional Quality, Processing and Potential Health Benefits*. Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1039/9781788015721-00001>.
- Meinlschmidt, P., Schweiggert-Weisz, U., Eisner, P., 2016a. Soy protein hydrolysates fermentation: effect of debittering and degradation of major soy allergens. *LWT* 71, 202–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2016.03.026>.
- Meinlschmidt, P., Ueberham, E., Lehmann, J., Schweiggert-Weisz, U., Eisner, P., 2016b. Immunoreactivity, sensory and physicochemical properties of fermented soy protein isolate. *Food Chem.* 205, 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.03.016>.
- Mtshali, P.S., Divol, B., Van Rensburg, P., Du Toit, M., 2010. Genetic screening of wine-related enzymes in lactobacillus species isolated from south african wines. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 108, 1389–1397. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2672.2009.04535.X>.
- Murthy, P.S., P., S.H., K. B., Kusumoto, K.I., 2019. Modulation of coffee flavor precursors by *Aspergillus oryzae* serine carboxypeptidases. *LWT* 113, 108312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2019.108312>.
- Murthy, P.S., Palakshappa, S.H., Padela, J., Kusumoto, K.I., 2020. Amelioration of cocoa organoleptics using *A.oryzae* cysteine proteases. *LWT* 120, 108919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2019.108919>.
- Nikolaïdis, A., Moschakis, T., 2018. On the reversibility of ethanol-induced whey protein denaturation. *Food Hydrocoll.* 84, 389–395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2018.05.051>.
- Nout, M.J.R., Motarjemi, Y., 1997. Assessment of fermentation as a household technology for improving food safety: a joint FAO/WHO workshop. *Food Control* 8, 221–226. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-7135\(97\)00021-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-7135(97)00021-2).
- Olsen, T.H., Yesiltas, B., Marin, F.I., Pertseva, M., García-Moreno, P.J., Gregersen, S., Overgaard, M.T., Jacobsen, C., Lund, O., Hansen, E.B., Marcatili, P., 2020. AnOxPePred: using deep learning for the prediction of antioxidative properties of peptides. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 21471. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78319-w>.
- Pérez Borla, O., Davidovich, L.A., Roura, S.I., 2010. Isolation and characterization of proteolytic microorganisms from fresh and fermented cabbage. *LWT* 43, 298–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2009.07.006>.
- Purushothaman, K., Bhat, S.K., Singh, S.A., Marathe, G.K., Appu Rao, A.R.G., 2019. Aspartic protease from aspergillus Niger: molecular characterization and interaction with pepstatin a. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 139, 199–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.07.133>.
- Qamar, S., Manrique, Y.J., Parekh, H., Falconer, J.R., 2020. Nuts, cereals, seeds and legumes proteins derived emulsifiers as a source of plant protein beverages: a review nuts, cereals, seeds and legumes proteins derived emulsifiers as a source of plant protein beverages: a review. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 60, 2742–2762. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2019.1657062>.
- Rao, M.B., Tanksale, A.M., Ghatge, M.S., Deshpande, V.V., 1998. Molecular and biotechnological aspects of microbial proteases. *Microbiol. Mol. Biol. Rev.* 62, 597–635. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MMBR.62.3.597-635.1998>.
- Reale, A., Di Stasio, L., Di Renzo, T., De Caro, S., Ferranti, P., Picariello, G., Addeo, F., Mamone, G., 2021. Bacteria do it better! Proteomics suggests the molecular basis for improved digestibility of sourdough products. *Food Chem.* 359, 129955 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2021.129955>.
- Remize, F., Augagneur, Y., Guilloux-Benatier, M., Guzzo, J., 2005. Effect of nitrogen limitation and nature of the feed upon oenococcus oeni metabolism and extracellular protein production. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 98, 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2672.2004.02494.X>.
- Rizzello, C.G., De Angelis, M., Di Cagno, R., Camarca, A., Silano, M., Losito, I., De Vincenzi, M., De Bari, M.D., Palmisano, F., Maurano, F., Gianfrani, C., Gobbetti, M., 2007. Highly efficient gluten degradation by lactobacilli and fungal proteases during food processing: new perspectives for celiac disease. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 73, 4499–4507. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00260-07>.
- Rizzello, C.G., Curiel, J.A., Nionelli, L., Vincentini, O., Di Cagno, R., Silano, M., Gobbetti, M., Coda, R., 2014. Use of fungal proteases and selected sourdough lactic acid bacteria for making wheat bread with an intermediate content of gluten. *Food Microbiol.* 37, 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2013.06.017>.
- Rizzello, C.G., Coda, R., Wang, Y., Verni, M., Kajala, I., Katina, K., Laitila, A., 2019. Characterization of indigenous pediococcus pentosaceus, leuconostoc kimchii, weissella cibaria and weissella confusa for faba bean bioprocessing. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 302, 24–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFOODMICRO.2018.08.014>.
- Rojas Tovar, L.E., Gänzle, M.G., 2021. Degradation of wheat germ agglutinin during sourdough fermentation. *Foods* 10, 340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10020340>.
- Rollán, G.C., Fariás, M.E., Manca de Nadra, M.C., 1993. Protease production by leuconostoc oenos strains isolated from wine. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 9, 587–589. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00386300>.
- Rollán, G.C., Fariás, M.E., De Nadra, M.C.M., 1995. Characterization of two extracellular proteases from leuconostoc oenos. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 11, 153–155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00704637>.
- Rollán, G.C., Fariás, M.E., Strasser De Saad, A.M., Manca De Nadra, M.C., 1998. Exoprotease activity of leuconostoc oenos in stress conditions. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 85, 219–223. <https://doi.org/10.1046/J.1365-2672.1998.00457.X>.
- Sabater, C., Ruiz, L., Delgado, S., Ruas-Madiedo, P., Margolles, A., 2020. Valorization of vegetable food waste and by-products through fermentation processes. *Front. Microbiol.* 11, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.581997>.
- Sabotic, J., Kos, J., 2012. Microbial and fungal protease inhibitors - current and potential applications. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 93, 1351–1375. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-011-3834-x>.
- Sanjukta, S., Rai, A.K., 2016. Production of bioactive peptides during soybean fermentation and their potential health benefits. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 50, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2016.01.010>.
- Scarnato, L., Serrazanetti, D.I., Aloisi, I., Montanari, C., Del Duca, S., Lanciotti, R., 2016. Combination of transglutaminase and sourdough on gluten-free flours to improve dough structure. *Amino Acids* 48, 2453–2465. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-016-2258-4>.
- Schlender, M., Distler, U., Tenzer, S., Thines, E., Claus, H., 2017. Purification and properties of yeast proteases secreted by wickerhamomyces anomalus 227 and metschnikovia pulcherrima 446 during growth in a white grape juice. *Fermentation* 3, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation3010002>.
- Schofield, J.D., 1994. Wheat proteins: structure and functionality in milling and breadmaking. In: Bushuk, W., Rasper, V.F. (Eds.), *Wheat*. Springer, Boston, pp. 73–106. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-2672-8_7.
- Sharma, P., Sharma, D., Amin, A., 2018. Development of a functional fermented peanut-based cheese analog using probiotic bacteria. *Biotechnologia* 99, 435–441. <https://doi.org/10.5114/BTA.2018.79973>.
- Shirovani, N., Bygvraa Hougaard, A., Lametsch, R., Agerlin Petersen, M., Rattray, F.P., Ipsen, R., 2021. Proteolytic activity of selected commercial lactobacillus helveticus strains on soy protein isolates. *Food Chem.* 340, 128152 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.128152>.
- Siezen, R.J., 1999. Multi-domain, cell-envelope proteinases of lactic acid bacteria. *Anton. Leeuw. Int. J. Gen. Mol. Microbiol.* 76, 139–155. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1002036906922>.
- Siezen, R.J., Leunissen, J.A.M., 2008. Subtilases: the superfamily of subtilisin-like serine proteases. *Protein Sci.* 6, 501–523. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.5560060301>.
- Son, E.Y., Lee, S.M., Kim, M., Seo, J.A., Kim, Y.S., 2018. Comparison of volatile and non-volatile metabolites in rice wine fermented by koji inoculated with saccharomyces fibuligera and aspergillus oryzae. *Food Res. Int.* 109, 596–605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.05.008>.
- Souza Cândido, E., Pinto, M.F.S., Pelegrini, P.B., Lima, T.B., Silva, O.N., Pogue, R., Grossi-de-Sá, M.F., Franco, O.L., 2011. Plant storage proteins with antimicrobial activity: novel insights into plant defense mechanisms. *FASEB J.* 25, 3290–3305. <https://doi.org/10.1096/FJ.11-184291>.
- Stefaniska, I., Piasecka-Józwiak, K., Kotyrba, D., Kolenda, M., Stecka, K.M., 2016. Selection of lactic acid bacteria strains for the hydrolysis of allergenic proteins of wheat flour. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 96, 3897–3905. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.7588>.
- Steinkraus, K.H., 2004. Origin and history of food fermentation. In: Hui, Y.H., Meunier-Goddik, L., Josephsen, J., Nip, W.K., Stanfield, P.S. (Eds.), *Handbook of Food and Beverage Fermentation Technology*. CRC Press, New York, pp. 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203913550>.
- Sumantha, A., Larroche, C., Pandey, A., 2006. *Microbiology and industrial biotechnology of food-grade proteases: a perspective*. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.* 44, 211–220.
- Tanguy, M., Muller, J., Bolten, C.J., Wittmann, C., 2019. Fermentation of plant-based milk alternatives for improved flavour and nutritional value. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 103, 9263–9275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-019-10175-9>.
- Vallabha, V.S., Tikur, P.K., 2014. Antihypertensive peptides derived from soy protein by fermentation. *Int. J. Pept. Res. Ther.* 20, 161–168. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10989-013-9377-5>.
- Van Schaick, G., Domínguez-Vega, E., Gstöttner, C., Van Den Berg-Verleg, J.H., Schouten, O., Akeroyd, M., Olsthoorn, M.M.A., Wührer, M., Heck, A.J.R., Abello, N., Franc, V., 2021. Native structural and functional proteoform characterization of the prolyl-alanyl-specific endoprotease EndoPro from aspergillus Niger. *J. Proteome Res.* 20, 4875–4885. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.1c00663>.
- Van Sluyter, S.C., McRae, J.M., Falconer, R.J., Smith, P.A., Bacic, A., Waters, E.J., Marangon, M., 2015. Wine protein haze: mechanisms of formation and advances in prevention. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 63, 4020–4030. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.5b00047>.
- Verni, M., Demarinis, C., Rizzello, C.G., Baruzzi, F., 2020. Design and characterization of a novel fermented beverage from lentil grains. *Foods* 9, 893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9070893>.

- Vong, W.C., Hua, X.Y., Liu, S.Q., 2018. Solid-state fermentation with *Rhizopus oligosporus* and *Yarrowia lipolytica* improved nutritional and flavour properties of okara. *LWT* 90, 316–322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.12.050>.
- World Health Organization, International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2003. Definitions and classifications for fruit and vegetables. In: *Fruit and Vegetables: IARC Handbooks of Cancer Prevention*. IARC Press, Lyon, France, pp. 1–21.
- Wouters, A.G.B., Rombouts, I., Fierens, E., Brijs, K., Delcour, J.A., 2016. Relevance of the functional properties of enzymatic plant protein hydrolysates in food systems. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 15, 786–800. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12209>.
- Wrigley, C., 2017. The cereal grains: providing our food, feed and fuel needs. In: Wrigley, C., Batey, I., Miskelly, D. (Eds.), *Cereal Grains: Assessing and Managing Quality*. Woodhead Publishing, pp. 27–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100719-8.00002-4>.
- Wu, H., Rui, X., Li, W., Xiao, Y., Zhou, J., Dong, M., 2018. Whole-grain oats (*Avena sativa* L.) as a carrier of lactic acid bacteria and a supplement rich in angiotensin I-converting enzyme inhibitory peptides through solid-state fermentation. *Food Funct.* 9, 2270. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7FO01578J>.
- Yang, L., Zhou, Y., Li, J., Liu, S., He, S., Sun, H., Yao, S., Xu, S., 2021. Effect of enzymes addition on the fermentation of Chinese rice wine using defined fungal starter. *LWT* 143, 111101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111101>.
- Yegin, S., Fernandez-Lahore, M., Jose Gama Salgado, A., Guvenc, U., Goksungur, Y., Tari, C., 2011. Aspartic proteinases from *Mucor* spp. in cheese manufacturing. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 89, 949–960. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-010-3020-6>.
- Yesiltas, B., Gregersen, S., Lægsgaard, L., Brinch, M.L., Olsen, T.H., Marcatili, P., Overgaard, M.T., Hansen, E.B., Jacobsen, C., García-Moreno, P.J., 2021. Emulsifier peptides derived from seaweed, methanotrophic bacteria, and potato proteins identified by quantitative proteomics and bioinformatics. *Food Chem.* 362, 130217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.130217>.
- Yin, L., Zhang, Y., Wu, H., Wang, Z., Dai, Y., Zhou, J., Liu, X., Dong, M., Xia, X., 2020. Improvement of the phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and nutritional quality of tofu fermented with *Actinomyces elegans*. *LWT* 133, 110087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.110087>.
- Younes, B., Cilindre, C., Jeandet, P., Vasserot, Y., 2013. Enzymatic hydrolysis of thermosensitive grape proteins by a yeast protease as revealed by a proteomic approach. *Food Res. Int.* 54, 1298–1301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2013.01.063>.
- Yu, P., Du, J., Cao, C., Guolin, C., Sun, J., Wu, D., Lu, J., 2021. Development of a novel multi-strain wheat qu with high enzyme activities for Huangjiu. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 101, 4808–4817. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.11127>.
- Zhang, K., Li, Q., Wu, W., Yang, J., Zou, W., 2019. Wheat qu and its production technology, microbiota, flavor, and metabolites. *J. Food Sci.* 84, 2373–2386. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.14768>.
- Zheng, J., Wittouck, S., Salvetti, E., Franz, C.M.A.P., Harris, H.M.B., Mattarelli, P., O’toole, P.W., Pot, B., Vandamme, P., Walter, J., Watanabe, K., Wuyts, S., Felis, G.E., Gänzle, M.G., Lebeer, S., 2020. A taxonomic note on the genus *Lactobacillus*: description of 23 novel genera, emended description of the genus *Lactobacillus* Beijerinck 1901, and union of *Lactobacillaceae* and *Leuconostocaceae*. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 70, 2782–2858. <https://doi.org/10.1099/IJSEM.0.004107>.